

Future Directions in Strategic Brand Management Research Using Bibliometric Analysis: A Decade Review

Resti Indriarti^{1*}, Ratih Hurriyati², Puspo Dewi Dirgantari³, Prasetyo Harisandi⁴

Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Indonesia | restiarti@upi.edu¹

Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Indonesia | ratihhurriyati@upi.edu²

Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Indonesia | puspodewidirgantari@upi.edu³

Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Indonesia | prasetyharisandi@upi.edu⁴

Correspondence Author*

Abstract

This research aim is to examine future directions in strategic brand management research through a bibliometric computational mapping analysis using VOS viewer. Publish or Perish reference manager application is used to retrieve the Google Scholar database in order to fulfill research data. The title and abstract of the article are used to provide guidance on the search process based on the keywords "Strategic Brand Management". The results showed 997 relevant articles. The search for publication data used as study material was carried out in the last ten years (2013-2023). The results also showed that there are two larger circles comparing others, namely "brand loyalty" and "business strategy". The term "brand loyalty" is associated with 15 links, 33 total link strength, and 30 occurrences, while the term "business strategy" is associated with 10 links, 33 total link strength, and 31 occurrences. The results of strategic brand management research in the last ten years show a declining trend, from 104 publications to 61 publications. There were only increase a little bit in 2015, from 104 publications to 115 publications, and increase in 20203, from 80 publications to 93 publications. Based on a downward trend, publications on strategic brand management in the last ten years were dominated by 2015 (115 publications). The results of this study are expected to inspire and develop the articles of related terms in the future.

Keywords: *Bibliometric, Brand Strategy, Computational Mapping Analysis, Strategic Brand Management*

Abstrak

Penelitian ini disusun untuk melihat arah masa depan penelitian mengenai Strategic Brand Management melalui pendekatan *bibliometric computational mapping analysis* menggunakan VOSviewer. Aplikasi Publish or Perish Reference Manager digunakan untuk mengambil

database Google Scholar dalam rangka pemenuhan data penelitian. Judul dan abstrak dari artikel digunakan untuk memberikan panduan proses pencarian berdasarkan kata kunci “Strategic Brand Management”. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan 997 artikel yang relevan. Pencarian data publikasi yang digunakan sebagai bahan kajian, dilakukan dalam kurun waktu sepuluh tahun terakhir, yaitu pada periode tahun 2013 hingga 2023. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa penelitian Strategic Brand Management memiliki 58 item, 8 clusters, 173 link/tautan. Hasil analisis menunjukkan penelitian Strategic Brand Management pada sepuluh tahun terakhir menunjukkan trend yang menurun, dari 104 publikasi menjadi 61 publikasi. Hanya terjadi satu kali peningkatan pada tahun 2017, yakni dari 89 publikasi menjadi 99 publikasi. Berdasarkan trend yang cenderung menurun, publikasi mengenai Strategic Brand Management dalam periode sepuluh tahun terakhir didominasi pada tahun 2015, yaitu 115 publikasi. Hasil penelitian ini diharapkan dapat menginspirasi dan mengembangkan tema artikel terkait dimasa depan.

Kata kunci: Bibliometrik, *Brand Strategy*, *Computational Mapping Analysis*, *Strategic Brand Management*

Introduction

Brand management has long been recognized as a crucial aspect of business strategy. A brand represents a company's identity, values, and promises to its consumers, making it a fundamental asset for achieving a competitive edge in the market. The management of these assets, commonly referred to as strategic brand management, is a dynamic and multifaceted field. The significance of strategic brand management research has only grown in recent years, driven by the ever-changing business landscape and the emergence of new technologies and communication channels. This introduction aims to shed light on the importance of conducting a bibliometric analysis in the field of Strategic Brand Management and why it is essential to investigate its future prospects.

To comprehend the relevance of strategic brand management in the contemporary business landscape, it is crucial to consider its history. Prior research has highlighted its central role in fostering brand loyalty, enhancing brand equity, and ultimately driving profitability (Keller, 1993; Aaker, 1991). Furthermore, strategic brand management has been recognized as a vital instrument for businesses aiming to differentiate themselves from competitors, attract customers, and establish a strong market presence (Kapferer, 1992; Fombrun, 1996).

Moreover, studies have illustrated that strategic brand management is indispensable for achieving organizational objectives. It influences various aspects of business performance, such as market share (Kapferer, 1992), consumer trust and loyalty (Keller, 1993), and overall brand health (Aaker, 1996). As businesses operate in an increasingly globalized and digitalized environment, strategic brand management has become even more critical for ensuring a company's continued relevance and success.

As the field of strategic brand management has grown, so has the body of research associated with it. A plethora of studies have been published, investigating various facets of brand management, including brand equity, brand positioning, brand communication, brand

loyalty, brand awareness, brand experience, brand communities, consumer perceptions of brands, and more. However, the sheer volume of research makes it challenging for scholars, practitioners, and decision-makers to keep up with the latest trends and insights in the field to make a future research director in strategic brand management (B. & D., 2014; Dessart, 2015; Gensler et al., 2013; Bruno Godey et al., 2016; Katja Hutter et al., 2013).

Bibliometric analysis offers a systematic and quantitative approach to understanding the structure, evolution, and impact of research in strategic brand management. By applying bibliometrics, we can identify key authors, journals, and influential studies, helping to map the intellectual landscape of the field. Moreover, this approach allows us to highlight emerging research trends and areas in need of further exploration. By exploring the future prospects of strategic brand management will not only guide businesses in their strategic decision-making but also provide a roadmap for researchers to address critical questions and gaps in the field.

Research Method

The data used in this study are research publications indexed by Google Scholar. As an open source, Google Scholar was chosen to access the database of publications that are the main study material for this research. The Google Scholar database is accessed via Publish or Perish Reference Manager Application.

In accordance with the title of the publication, the search for article data with the keywords “Strategic Brand Management” is carried out through the help of the Publish or Perish Reference Manager Application. The publications used as research study materials are related publications published within the last ten years, namely in the range of 2013 to 2023. Data were obtained and processed in November 2023. The VOS viewer application is used to visualize and evaluate future direction in strategic brand management research using a bibliometric analysis with the results of three visualizations.

Results and Discussion

Publication Data Search Results

Based on the search results of the Google Scholar database through the Publish or Perish Reference Manager application, 997 articles relevant to the research criteria were obtained. The data obtained is in the form of article metadata consisting of the author's name, title, year of publication, journal name, publisher name, number of citations, article links, and related links. Table 1 shows some examples of publications used in the VOSviewer analysis of this study. The data samples taken were the 30 best publications that had the highest number of citations. The number of citations from all articles used in this study is 53407, the number of citations per year is 5340.70, the number of citations per article is 53.57, the average author in published articles is 2.46, all publications have an average h-index of 115 and g-index 195.

Table 1. The 30 Highest Number of Citation on Strategic Brand Management Publication

No.	Authors & Year	Title	Cites
1	(B Godey et al., 2016)	Social media marketing efforts of luxury brands: Influence on brand equity and consumer behavior	1815
2	(K Hutter et al., 2013)	The impact of user interactions in social media on brand awareness and purchase intention: the case of MINI on Facebook	1388
3	(Wirtz et al., 2013)	Managing brands and customer engagement in online brand communities	1017
4	(Braun et al., 2013)	My city–my brand: the different roles of residents in place branding	951
5	(Buil et al., 2013)	The influence of brand equity on consumer responses	718
6	(Zhang, 2015)	The impact of brand image on consumer behavior: A literature review	705
7	(Hur et al., 2014)	How CSR leads to corporate brand equity: Mediating mechanisms of corporate brand credibility and reputation	685
8	(Ko et al., 2019)	What is a luxury brand? A new definition and review of the literature	615
9	(Leckie et al., 2016)	Antecedents of consumer brand engagement and brand loyalty	578
10	(Ramaswamy & Ozcan, 2016)	Brand value co-creation in a digitalized world: An integrative framework and research implications	554
11	(Urde et al., 2013)	Brand orientation and market orientation—From alternatives to synergy	543
12	(Nysveen et al., 2013)	Brand experiences in service organizations: Exploring the individual effects of brand experience dimensions	534
13	(Becerra & Badrinarayanan, 2013)	The influence of brand trust and brand identification on brand evangelism	534
14	(Fritz et al., 2017)	Authenticity in branding—exploring antecedents and consequences of brand authenticity	501
15	(Lundqvist et al., 2013)	The impact of storytelling on the consumer brand experience: The case of a firm-originated story	477
16	(Ekinci et al., 2013)	Symbolic consumption of tourism destination brands	443
17	(Silveira et al., 2013)	Reconceptualizing brand identity in a dynamic environment	435
18	(Sydler et al., 2014)	Measuring intellectual capital with financial figures: can we predict firm profitability?	412
19	(Eggers et al., 2013)	The impact of brand authenticity on brand trust and SME growth: A CEO perspective	391
20	(Lam et al., 2013)	Exploring the dynamics of antecedents to consumer–brand identification with a new brand	382
21	(Wijaya, 2013)	Dimensions of brand image: A conceptual review from the perspective of brand communication	372
22	(Swaminathan et al., 2020)	Branding in a hyperconnected world: Refocusing theories and rethinking boundaries	359

No.	Authors & Year	Title	Cites
23	(France et al., 2016)	An integrated model of customer-brand engagement: Drivers and consequences	333
24	(Alhaddad, 2015)	Perceived quality, brand image and brand trust as determinants of brand loyalty	328
25	(Ebrahim et al., 2016)	A brand preference and repurchase intention model: the role of consumer experience	326
26	(Dwivedi et al., 2015)	Celebrity endorsement, self-brand connection and consumer-based brand equity	322
27	(Gyrd-Jones & Kornum, 2013)	Managing the co-created brand: Value and cultural complementarity in online and offline multi-stakeholder ecosystems	320
28	(Urde, 2013)	The corporate brand identity matrix	315
29	(Lin, 2015)	Innovative brand experience's influence on brand equity and brand satisfaction	305
30	(Baalbaki & Guzmán, 2016)	A consumer-perceived consumer-based brand equity scale	278

Research Number on Strategic Brand Management

Table 2 shows the research number on Strategic Brand Management published in journals indexed by Google Scholar. Based on the data attached to Table 2, it can be seen that in the last ten years (2013-2023) the number of research publications on strategic brand management was 997 articles. In 2013 and 2014 there were 104 publications each year. In 2015 there were 115 publications. In 2016 there were 108 publications. In 2017 there were 82 publications. In 2018 there were 93 publications. In 2019 there were 80 publications. In 2020 there were 93 publications. In 2021 there were 87 publications. In 2022 there were 70 publications., and in 2023 (until November 2023) there were 61 publications. From the number of publications, it can be concluded that research on strategic brand management has a trend that tends to decline, especially in the last ten years.

Table 2. Number of Publication on Strategic Brand Management

Year of Publications	Number of Publications
2013	104
2014	104
2015	115
2016	108
2017	82
2018	93
2019	80
2020	93
2021	87
2022	70
2023	61
Total	997
Average	90,64

Computational Mapping Visualization on Strategic Brand Management Using VOS Viewer

Computational mapping analysis was performed on published data using VOS viewer. Through this study, there are three parts of mapping visualization analyzed, namely: network visualization (see Fig.1), density visualization (see Fig.4) and overlay visualization (see Fig.5). The results of the computational mapping analysis found that there were 54 relevant items. In mapping the publication data, each item found regarding strategic brand management researches was divided into eight clusters, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Eight Clusters on Strategic Brand Management Publication

Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 6
1. Brand authenticity	1. Brand co-creation	1. Advertising	1. Brand management system	1. Brand architecture
2. Brand building	2. Branding strategy	2. Brand attachment	2. Brand orientation	2. Corporate brand
3. Brand communication	3. Integrated marketing communication	3. Brand attitude	3. Brand performance	3. Product brand
4. Brand extension	4. Internet	4. Brand credibility	4. Employer branding	
5. Brand love	5. Marketing communication	5. Brand experience	5. Internal branding	Cluster 7
6. Brand manager	6. New product	6. Brand familiarity	6. Market orientation	1. Brand loyalty
7. Brand perception	7. New strategic brand marketing	7. Brand trust		2. Customer satisfaction
8. Brands	8. Social media platform	8. Celebrity endorsement	Cluster 5	3. Quality
9. Change	9. New strategic brand management	9. Mediating role	1. Brand strategy	
10. Consumer response	10. Strong brand	10. Purchase intention	2. Medium sized enterprise	Cluster 8
11. Customer loyalty	11. Uniqueness		3. Retailer	1. Corporate Social Responsibility
12. Marketing strategy			4. SME	2. CSR
13. Strategic brand management			5. SME'S	
14. Technology				

Figure 1 shows the relationship between terms described in an interconnected network. Figure 1 also shows the clusters of each term studied on the research topic of strategic brand management. The relationship between one term and another is shown in each existing cluster. Labels are assigned to each term with colored circles.

Figure 1. Network Visualization of Strategic Brand Management Research

The size of the dot for each term varies depending on the frequency of occurrence of the term (Nandiyanto et al., 2021). For example, in this study there are two larger dots comparing others, namely brand loyalty and brand orientation. That means regarding brand loyalty and brand orientation appears often on strategic brand management research. Meanwhile terms such as customer satisfaction, product brand, brand trust, retailer, brand co-creation, and brand management system still rarely appear on strategic brand management research. The size of the dots' label shows a positive correlation with the occurrence of terms in the title and abstract (Nandiyanto & Al Husaeni, 2021). The larger the size of the label, the more often the term is found (Al Husaeni & Nandiyanto, 2022).

As the term that appears most frequently in strategic brand management research, it can be seen that the term of brand loyalty is in cluster 7 and divided to 15 links, 33 total link strength, and 30 occurrences (see Fig 2). While the term business strategy is in cluster 4 and divided to 10 links, 33 total link strength, and 31 occurrences (see Fig 3).

Figure 2. Network Visualization of Business Loyalty Term

Figure 3. Network Visualization of Business Orientation Term

Figure 4 shows the density visualization. Density means that the more often a term appears, it will show the brighter yellow color, and the larger the diameter of the dot (Mulyawati & Ramadhan, 2021; Nandiyanto et al., 2021; Nandiyanto & Al Husaeni, 2021; Schrlau et al., 2016). This means that there has been a lot of research on related terms. On the other hand, if the number of studies on a term is still relatively small, the color of the term will fade closer to the background color. Based on Figure 4, we can see that research related to the term brand loyalty and brand orientation has a high number of studies.

Figure 4. Density Visualization of Strategic Brand Management Research

Figure 5. Overlay Visualization of Strategic Brand Management Research

Figure 5 shows the overlay visualization of strategic brand management research. The brighter colour shows that the terms is become popular in the current years, while the darker colour shows that the terms no longer popular in the current years. However, the popularity of strategic brand management publications over the last ten years, has been around for a long time, namely in 2015. Therefore, this should be our inspiration to develop publications with the theme of strategic brand management, and also to create the research novelty, such as mentioned on previous research that overlay visualization shows the novelty on related terms (Nandiyanto, et al., 2021; Nandiyanto, and Al Husaeni, D. F., 2021; Al Husaeni, D. F., & Nandiyanto, 2022). However, the trend of strategic brand management publication, which has been declining in the last ten years, still needs to be developed and updated. Thus, this will have a higher impact on the research novelty and future research direction.

Conclusion

This study was to perform computational mapping analysis on the bibliometric data of research articles. The publication theme taken in this research were strategic brand management. The articles used are taken from the Google Scholar database via the Publish or Perish Reference Manager Application. The results of the data search found that there were 997 relevant articles published in the range 2013 until 2023. The results showed that publications on the strategic brand management tended to experience a declining trend in the last ten years. This shows that there is still a high opportunity to update research on strategic brand management, especially those associated with terms such as customer satisfaction, product brand, brand trust, retailer, brand co-creation, and brand management system.

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